
**COMPARATIVE STUDY ON DEPRESSION, LIFE SATISFACTION
AFTER RETIREMENT AMONG WORKING AND NON-WORKING
PEOPLE**

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7648232

Abstract:

This study attempts to find out the comparison between depression, life satisfaction among post-working and non-working people after retirement. This study is an attempt to find if working after retirement has an impact on psychological well-being of the elderly. Total sample of 73, both working and non-working, taken from different areas. Tools include Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS-short form) by Yesavage and Satisfaction with Life Scale by Diener, Emmons, Larsen and Griffith. The result suggests working post retirement is a positive factor in maintaining psychological well-being in the elderly.

Keywords: *Depression, Life satisfaction, Working, Non-working, Retirement, Aging*

Introduction:

One of the most significant events in the life of the aging man is retirement. Even though retirement brings about some expected disruptions in the life of a person, it is obvious that some are more affected than others are (Atchley, 1976). Retirement is clearly listed as one of the stressful life events when a person feels discriminated from a society and must undergo numerous readjustments. It is then but natural to experience symptoms of anxiety, depression, shattered self-esteem.

Aging is a global phenomenon. It is no longer limited to any industrialised

societies. The population of elderly is growing everywhere. The world is experiencing actual demographic greying of the planet. India's population is likely to rise in next 50 years and the number of elders above 60 will shoot dramatically. India has 100 million elderlies today and this figure will raise constituting 20% of India's population by 2050.

Reducing physical capacities, changing role in the family and society, financial dependency of children and lack of opportunities to use their knowledge and wisdom can bring new challenges in front of the elderly. A lot of unutilised free

time can add on to this challenge. Hence, readjustment with family and society and channelizing their resources is essential. Cox (1984) states that some of the problems are lowering of income, loss of status, loss of privilege, reorganization of daily activities, changing perception of self, social isolation and sense of meaninglessness.

One major change is brought about in the life of elderly due to retirement from work. Work provides us with inner joy of achieving something. It saves us from dullness and boredom of life and helps channelize our energy. Retirement not only leads to financial crunches but also creates hollowness in the life of an elderly. Various aspects in person's life both pre and post retirement can determine their adjustment to it. One such important aspect in the post retirement life is the kind of activities in which elderly involve themselves. Staying connected with others is important benefit of work. Co-workers play an important role in maintaining social relationships.

History and Evolution:

Retirement has steadily grown in importance in industrial societies. It has changed from a rare and novel social pattern to a practically universal social institution it can be viewed as a process, event, social role, or a phase of life.

Retirement is a creation of industrial society. In the preindustrial era people did indeed stop working because of old age but there was no way that a person could earn the right to an income (pension) without doing a job or owning enough property to provide it. In early societies, older people were supported only so long as they could perform some sort of productive function. For e.g., if the Eskimos grandmother could no longer chew the hide for boots she would be abandoned (Donahue, Orbach, 1960). The advent of an agricultural society brought two important developments – an economic surplus and the concept of property. Thus, older people who had gained property rights could support themselves in old age because they had the power of ownership. Those who lived to become old tended to be from the upper economic strata in which financial power had traditionally been used to support the lower economic strata of population. But the labourer who did not have property rights and could no longer work had to fall back on the benevolence of their family and well-to-do members of society. Industrialization brought many changes. Industrial form of production drastically increased available economic surplus. The main reasons for this increase in productivity were man's discovery of nonhuman energy to produce goods. As

urbanization increased and fertility rates declined, with a decrease in mortality, a larger proportion of the population was in the older age group. Industrialization upset the system of older people retaining power. In industrial society people from all walks of life survived to become old. Industrialization decreased the power of older people by divorcing management from ownership and putting a cover premium on experience. Therefore, the scientific revolution destroyed the role of elders as bridges to the dead generation.

The rise of corporations and large-scale organizations for production eliminated the family with its patriarchal head as a typical unit of production. This paved the way for the argument that people should be relieved of their duties in old age because they were no longer capable of meeting minimum standards. Industrialization helped to dissociate the concept of work or work from the concept of life itself. Craftsmanship was the ideal of work in the pre-industrial era. The craftsman was the master of a product and the process of creating it. Industrialization reduced the job for many people to a fragment of a process. For workers in corporations or government bureaucracies, jobs moved towards being an element of life instead of a craft around which one's life revolved (Mills, 1956). People were living long enough to contribute to the

necessary work in an economy and still have several potentially productive years of life left. The rationalization of labour, the decline of entrepreneurship and the rise of a secular city meant that it was neither always possible nor desirable for individuals to hold a job into old age. People, thus, began to accept without guilt the concept of retirement as an earned right. Also, during the era of industrialization, concerns regarding human efficiency led to studies of the physical and mental decline caused by aging. Old age was increasingly depicted as a period of decline, weakness, inactivity, and dependency rather than wisdom and fulfillment. Child labour laws and compulsory education led to the segregation of the young while mandatory retirement age contributed to evolution of the elderly. This led to the creation and eventual acceptance of negative stereotypes of old ages. (Haravan, 1995) In India, old age is recognized as a source of prestige and honour where elders are respected and given authority in family and household matters.

The Ashram Theory of life in India presents a systematic approach to life developmental forms, namely brahmacharya, Grihastha, Vanaprastha and Sanyas – recognize withdrawal from society as an approach to old age. Japan, due to Buddhism has a similar pattern of

respect for the aged. In Japan, the head of the family seeks retirement called 'Inkyo' (retirement from active services) which is comparable to Vanprastha. Inkyo is a legal and social status. Due to industrialization and urbanization these old traditions have become perfunctory. At the start of the century, only a few people lived up to 65 yrs. and hence they did not cause a social problem. Therefore, men died before they reached the age of retirement, when it did occur, it was limited to the higher income brackets. Today, the retired are faced with making major adjustments to a world based on principles alien to the traditional socialization (Nagar, 1989).

Review of Literature:

There are many studies done in western countries, but hardly few studies were published from Asian countries that looked into retirement and mental health. Most of the studies were done on elderly who were going to retire and followed up them few years after retirement and assessed them for mental health. Majority of the studies reported that retirement had positive impact on mental health and quality of life.

Rina Pranay Patel in her research of 2018 article focused on impact of post retirement work on psychological well-being of elderly. In her research data is collected by initially approaching

approximately 50 elderly and by screening them on the defined criteria, 20 each are then selected in the two groups of the independent variable by following the standard procedures of data collection. Demographic information sheet and Ryff scale of psychological well-being are the tools that are used while this study. The results show that there is significant difference between the two groups on their psychological well-being. The mean of the scores for psychological well-being of the elderly involved in post-retirement work is 202.25 and that of the elderly not involved in post-retirement work is 163.35. the t value is 5.37 ($p < 0.01$).

Employment after retirement in India – an empirical study by Dr. Madhu Gupta in 2021 looked at the reasons for working or non-working after retirement. The study's primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire from 176 participants using a Google form, then analysed and presented using statistical techniques. Using Ms-Excel, the data was analysed using percentages, graphical presentations, frequency distribution, and cross tabulation. According to their research, a large majority of the elderly do not work after retirement (62 %). Elderly in India are often more content and do not have many demands. They desire to live a peaceful life after retirement, where they

can pursue their passions and do things they could not do while working.

Significance of the Study:

Today population of old age is increasing constantly, so there is need to create awareness about their mental health. Also elderly people feel that young generation treat them disrespectfully. After retirement their value in family decreases because they are not more earning or contributing financially. They also have question in front of them that what to do in free time after retirement. And because of earlier they were busy in work but now suddenly they have lot of time it leads to disturbance in their schedule. And this all can leads to psychological disorders

Statement of Problem:

1. To examine the possible comparison between mental health of working and non-working people after retirement.

Objectives:

The study intended to throw light on the mental health of working and non-working people after retirement. Considering above-mentioned statement of problem following objectives of the study have been made.

1. To study the impact of post-work on mental health of the retired people.
2. To study the significant differences in working and non-working people with respect to depression and life satisfaction.
3. To assess whether people who are working after retirement are less prone to depression and have high life satisfaction.

Hypotheses:

H1: People working after retirement score less on depression than people not working.

H2: People working after retirement score more on life satisfaction than people not working.

Sample:

The method which is used for collecting samples is accidental sampling method which is also known as incidental sampling and snowball method. The respondents were personally approached by me. The questionnaires were given to them to solve in front of me. Total sample size is 73. Age ranging between 55 and above overall population with socioeconomic background is considered too. The sampling was done in Pune. The samples included both males and females.

All the demographic details were asked in personal data sheet.

Variables:

- Independent variable
Work after retirement
- Dependent variable
Depression
Life Satisfaction

Tools:

Two questionnaires used in this study. One is Geriatric Depression Scale and other is Satisfaction with Life Scale.

Depression: Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS) first created by Yesavage et al has been tested and used extensively with older population. A short form GDS consisting of 15 questions was developed in 1986. Of the 15 items, 10 indicated the presence of depression when answered positively, while the rest (question numbers 1, 5, 7, 11, 13) indicated depression when answered negatively. Scores 0-4 are considered normal, depending on education, age, and complaints; 5-8 indicate mild depression; 9-11 indicate moderate depression; and 12-15 indicate severe depression. The GDS was found to have a 92% sensitivity and an 89% specificity when evaluated against diagnostic criteria. The scale has Cronbach alpha =0.89 and ($r=.84 < .001$)

Life Satisfaction:

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) is a short 5-item instrument designed to measure global cognitive judgements of satisfaction with one's life. The respondents answer on a Likert scale. Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffith (1985) have conducted a series of validation studies showing that the SWLS has a single factor, high internal consistency, is reliable and is content appropriate for a wide range of groups. The SWLS is reported to have very good internal consistency, with an alpha of 0.87 and excellent test reliability, with a correlation of 0.82. Scores consist of a raw score (between 5 and 35). High scores represent higher life satisfaction. Scorers can be assigned into six well-being categories and interpretative text is provided for each.

Procedure:

The Geriatric Depression Scale short form was used to determine depression among old age people. It is valid and reliable test and used extensively for old age population.

Satisfaction With Life Scale was used to examine life satisfaction levels among old age population. Is a short 5-item instrument designed to measure global cognitive judgements of satisfaction with one's life.

The rapport was established with the respondents and it was made sure that all the information is only for academic

Statistical Analysis:

➤ Descriptive Statistics:

TABLE1: The table shows Mean and Standard Deviation of Depression, Life Satisfaction.

VARIABLE		WORKIN G	NON- WORKING
DEPRESSION	MEAN	1.74	8.66
	STADEV	1.63	2.56
SATISFACTION	MEAN	32.09	25.54
	STADEV	2.57	5.33

The above table shows the difference between mean and standard deviation of the working and non-working people.

➤ Inferential Statistics:

TABLE 2: The table shows t-value and significance of the sample.

VARIABLE	t- value	Sig.
DEPRESSION	11.879	< 0.001
SATISFACTION	-5.583	< 0.001

Results and Discussions:

The mean score of working population on depression scale (1.74) is lower than that of the non-working population on the depression scale is (8.66). This shows that people involved in post-retirement work suffer less from depression. Therefore, this obviously means hypothesis that people working after retirement score less on depression than people not working is accepted.

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purpose and all their information will be kept strictly confidential.

The t-value of depression (11.879) with a significance value of (< 0.001) that means it is highly significant and generalizable in population.

The mean score of working population on life satisfaction scale (32.09) is higher than the mean score of non-working population (25.54). Therefore, the hypothesis that people working after retirement score more on life satisfaction than people not working is accepted.

The t- value measures the size of the difference relative to the variation in the sample data. The t-value of life satisfaction (-5.583) with a significance value of (< 0.001) that means it is highly significant and generalizable in population. Therefore, research shows that the dependent variables are affected by independent variable.

Conclusion:

People involved in post- retirement work have less depression. People not involved in post-retirement have more depression. Also, people actively working have high life satisfaction. On the other hand, people not actively involved in work have less life satisfaction.

Limitations:

1. The study was done only in urban area of Pune.
2. Most of the samples were from high socio-economic background.
3. All variables in the family and work life of the elderly are not considered.
4. Sample size is small and the number of working and non-working people are not equal.

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